

Not Just A Teacher: The Changing Role of English Teacher in The 21st Century

Mr. Noojilla Srinivas,
Lecturer in English,
Govt. Degree College, Alamuru
Ph.D. Research Scholar in JNTU
Kakinada

Prof. T. Ashok
Dept. of English
Adikavi Nannaya University
MSN Campus
Kakinada

Introduction

The profession of teacher is one that existed since ancient times. The teacher's role has been changing and evolving through the ages depending upon the changes in the Political, Economic, Socio-cultural, and Technological areas in the society. Though the fundamental characteristics of a teacher or guru do not change much, his role keeps evolving to meet the challenges of the times faced by the educators and the expectations of the society. Hence, the teacher's role changes vis-à-vis the learner and the external environment.

Traditional and General roles played by a Teacher:

Let us first look at the general role played by any teacher irrespective of the subject he teaches. Even in the olden days also a teacher's role was not just limited to teaching or explaining the given subject or topic. But he was expected to don many roles as a friend, philosopher, and guide to his students. A teacher's traditional roles include:

- (a) **A provider of Knowledge and Skills** - A teacher of any subject is expected to provide knowledge that is authentic, latest, proven, and useful, skills that are useful for employment in the chosen field of teaching – learning process.
- (b) **A role model to students** – A teacher with his own behavior, value system and professional ethics, should act as a role model to his students. The students learn more from the teacher's behavior and true personality than from his classroom textbook based teaching. Hence, the society has always expected the teacher to act as a role model who can play an instrumental role in building a just and healthy society.
- (c) **An evaluator** – A teacher not only limits himself to teaching the subject knowledge but dons the role of an evaluator continuously. The evaluation done by the teacher can be formal and informal. The teacher is the best person to assess the improvement of the ward in the given subject. Based on the objectives of learning, the teacher assesses whether the student has acquired what he is expected to acquire.
- (d) **A supporter and a Counselor**– A teacher is always the supporter and helper to his students. Starting from elementary stage to the Graduate level and even beyond, the teacher's role in moulding the personality of the student is very crucial. The teacher only comes to the rescue when the student does any wrong, feels disheartened, suffers from low morale, lacks the confidence, and falls behind the learning objectives. Then the teacher becomes a counselor and advises the student towards the right path.
- (e) **A planner** – The traditional teacher's role involves planning the teaching – learning program, i.e., planning the curriculum based on the expected standards of a student, planning the right methods of teaching, planning for the utilization of right teaching tools and teaching resources, planning for the evaluation system, planning for the remedial coaching, planning for the progress of the students, etc.
- (f) **A developer** - A Teacher is the developer of curriculum, teaching – learning methodology, teaching learning processes, techniques, tools, resources, and evaluation systems, etc.
- (g) **A motivator** – A teacher motivates a student to realise his potential and reach the objectives of the learning process, as well as his personal dreams and goals by supporting him at every step and by inculcating positive spirit and hardworking nature

(h) **A partner** – *The ancient Indian system considers the teacher (Guru) and the student (disciple) as the partners of learning. The Upanishad points out the true relationship of the teacher and students. The Upanishadik sloka “Sahana vavathu, sahanou Bhunaktu, Saha Veeryam Karavaavahai, Tejaswinaa vadheetamastu Mavidweshavahai Om Shanti, Shanti, Shanti”* – exemplifies the roles of teachers and students as equal partners of the learning process. This sloka’s meaning is thus:

“Sahana vavathu = Let us live together

sahanou Bhunaktu = Let us participate or rejoice together

Saha Veeryam Karavaavahai = Let us acquire knowledge together

Tejaswinaa vadheetamastu = Let our education become dynamic”

Mavidweshavahai = Let not hatred divide us

Shanti, shanti, Shanti = Let there be peace, peace, peace

Interestingly, this Upanishadic advice is in accordance with the modern educational psychology and instructional strategy that teaching should not be a mass operation or a monologue without pupil’s participation. ‘Learning’ to be effective should be self-discovery on the basis of dialogue, questioning and personalized and individualized methods of instruction (which are propagated by the modern CLT- Communicative Language Teaching). The term Upanishad itself means “sitting together and discussing a problem” in a relaxed atmosphere.

The above said are the guiding principles as well as different roles donned by a teacher in general in all times. These general traits and functions are expected by the English teacher also, in the olden days.

Features of 21st Century – Changes in PEST – Influence of LPG – Advent of IT&C:

The 21st century is witnessing many revolutionary changes in Political, Economic, Socio-cultural, and Technological (PEST) aspects across the globe. All these changes have their strong impact and influence on education system and teaching-learning process, and the teacher- student relation. Politics became more democratized across the world and the spirit of democracy is reflected in the classrooms too. This gave prominence to learner- centered teaching methods. The socio-cultural changes removed the barriers of caste, community, race, religion and nation in the classrooms. Now, the classrooms have become more egalitarian, heterogeneous and humane. The cultural changes have removed the barriers between Western and Eastern cultures and acceptance of other cultures has become easier now. The economic changes mainly in the 21st century brought new paradigm shifts – named as the LPG era – era of Liberalisation, Privatisation, and Globalisation. This paradigm shift not only removed the barriers and controls between countries but also made the whole world a small village with the advent of Information and Communication Technology and Internet. All these technological changes have brought revolutionary changes in the field of education – as they removed geographical barriers between the teacher and the taught and also provided abundant teaching-learning resources, online classrooms, etc.

More than any other aspect, the 21st century witnessed how technology has provided more opportunities in education, and how insightful teachers maximize these opportunities for teaching and professional learning. The teachers who are committed to students and their learning will incorporate the formal and informal learning opportunities available both in the class rooms and outside. These days, the students learn informally outside school either through their "real world" or online experiences. Besides their hard cover printed books, they use Kindle or iPad. They like to work more on the computer, whether it is games, social networking, or watching instructional online videos on how to use technology on YouTube. All these transformed our way of interacting with the students in the classroom and outside the classroom.

The technology in the 21st century will allow the effective teachers to bridge the learning experiences more naturally and seamlessly. As more digital tools become available and technologies that facilitate learning in multiple modalities through synchronous or asynchronous online environments become more prevalent and accessible, 21st century teachers will continue seeking additional tools and avenues to improve

student learning. Technology in the 21st century maximizes additional opportunities through online teacher networks such as the **Teacher Leaders Network, Classroom 2.0**, and any number of teacher groups and forums on the Internet. The Internet and social networks bring a level of policy engagement on a much higher scale than previously possible. The tools may be different, but the commitment, learning, enthusiasm, and student focus are the same.

Changing Role of Teacher in the 21st Century:

The 21st century is an era of globalization strongly supported by the Information and Communication Technology and Internet. It is therefore essential to improve the sustainable education. The technology is changing rapidly. Hence, the teacher needs to guide the students in improving their employability skills with the digital tools. Thus a teacher in the twenty-first century will be a digital teacher. Teachers are not only the facilitators of learning for the students, but also the trainers of the students for increasing employability skills, expanding the mind, growing digital citizenships, critical thinking, and creativity as well as sustainable learning.

The differences between the traditional learning process and the current learning process also require new skills for the teacher:

The differences between Traditional teacher/ learner and the 21st century Teacher/learner are given below by the education website www.edutech.ac

	Traditional Teacher/Learner	21st Century Teacher/Learner
1	Sit and Get	Move and Experiment
2	Learner as receptor	Learner as initiator
3	Expectation save for all	Students Movigates Choices
4	Teachers Tell	Students Construct Meaning
5	Product Oriented	Process and Product Oriented
6	Paper/Pencil Driven	Technology Enhanced Learning and Multimedia Driven
7	Explicit Directions	No Limits
8	Isolated Learning Private	Shared Globally Collaborators
9	Complaint	Problem Solver
10	Answers are primary	Questions are primary
11	Closed System	Open System
12	Stayed the same	Changes Constantly
13	Knows facts	Inquirer
14	There is a right way	No right way
15	Wait for results	Immediate Gratification

www.edutech.ac

With the integration of technology in every sector, the teacher's role has changed a lot. They need to enrich some skills to develop their students. Otherwise, the students will not reach the expected goals, and it will increase the number of educated unemployed in the digital era. Let's see the changing role of a teacher in the 21st century. These roles are in addition to the traditional roles played by the teacher:

1. **A guide for 21st Century Careers – Today, the teachers of English language, right from the school level to University level, are expected to guide their wards in their future careers. As English language is becoming more important as a medium of learning as well as professional work, this new role is naturally expected by the present society and educational institutions.**
2. **A Resource Provider – The new careers require new skills and new resources to learn them. As a person handling multiple roles as a career counselor, soft skills trainer, organizer of English club, etc.,**

the teacher of English is expected to provide the required resources for the day to day learning and specialized skills both offline and online.

3. **A digital Instructor for Different Ways of Learning** – The teaching in the present century is not just limited to chalk and board. The students are learning through different devices and different ways. Hence, the teachers need to be digital instructors – be able to provide the content through digital devices, social media, IT-enabled learning management systems, standalone and seamless systems, in a collaborated environment.
4. **Learning Facilitator** – Today's Teacher of English is more a facilitator than an instructor or traditional teacher. Since the Student's Talk Time is to be more, the teacher's role changes as facilitator of learning. Further, the Teacher of English is expected to assist or in collaboration with his colleagues of other subjects. Therefore, here also, he acts a facilitator.
5. **A Technology Lover for Learning-** Today's teacher of English cannot avoid technology from his teaching- learning process. Given the nature of the spread and usage of English language through technological devices like Computers, Internet, Smart Phones, IPads, etc., the teacher should not see the technology as an obstacle. But, he should leverage the technology for better instruction.
6. **A digital Learner for the lifetime** – A lifelong learner only can become a good teacher. There are ample opportunities for the teachers of English to learn and update regularly using digital resources which are either free or of lesser cost. Hence, the teachers of English should explore this opportunity to be a competitive trainer in his field.
7. **A genuine predictor** – The teachers of English should be in a position to predict the changes in the teaching learning process and mould their methods accordingly. By bringing innovative technology enabled methods, they should provide the knowledge and skills required by the students and develop right attitude among them so that they can apply the acquired knowledge and skills properly in day to day lives.

Importance of English language in the 21st Century:

Though English has been on the top position as a global language for the last few centuries, it has become more relevant as an international language due to the increased network among the countries through technology, travel, business and social networks. English has become a universal language and is taught in all countries. Increased Career opportunities to the English speaking youth have helped in the growth of English language learning. Thus, English language has become very important language in the 21st century.

In the initial centuries, English was treated as a language of basic communication, later it was looked at as a language of different literature. In 20th century, English became the medium of higher education. In the 21st century, English has become the most sought after lingua franca and the gateway of other subjects and fields.

English has become a language of ENGLISH in the 21st century. This concept has been elaborated further below:

In the present era, English has become a language of ENGLISH, i.e., to say – English has become the language of:

- E-** Education, Employment and Empowerment
- N-** National interface and Network language
- G** –Governments and Global world
- L** – Libraries and Literature
- I** – Industries, Information Technology
- S** – Science and Technology
- H** – Hospitality

In view of the explanation provided above, English language has not only become the widest global language but also the most sought after language in the modern world.

Role of English teacher in 21st Century:

In view of the revolutionary changes in political, Socio cultural, Economic and Technological aspects, and also in view of the growing importance to English language, the English teachers need to play different roles. These roles are in addition to the traditional roles played by any teacher plus changed roles of all teachers in the 21st century. They are elaborated below:

- (a) **The Controller** – Teacher is the center/ focus
- (b) **The Prompter** - The teacher encourages students to participate and makes suggestions
- (c) **The Resource** - walking resource center ready to offer help if needed to the students during their communicative activities
- (d) **The Assessor** – evaluates the performance of the students from time to time with an objective to improve their skills
- (e) **The Organiser** – The teacher plans, designs, implements teaching learning activities and encourages the students participate in them, and assesses their capacities and learnings through observation and tests
- (f) **The Participant** – The teacher equally takes part in the communicative activities as a participant, along with the students
- (g) **The Tutor** – He helps the students in their project works, self studies

English teacher as SMART Skills Trainer:

English teacher in the 21st century is no more a teacher who is just limited to the role of teaching English language, literature and communication skills. He is expected to don many different roles – such as Corporate trainer, Placement Officer, Placement Manager, etc., due to the importance gained by English language as the sure winner of jobs and careers. The following are the novel roles being acted by the English Language Teachers.

The English teacher is expected to act as a SMART Skills TRAINER -

S- Soft Skills Trainer

M – Management Skills Trainer

A – Analytical Skills trainer

R – Research Skills trainer

T – Technical skills trainer (pertaining to usage of Computer and Android apps to learn language skills)

Thus, in the 21st century, the role of English teacher has changed to such an extent that today English teacher is considered a God who enables the students to win jobs and develop careers with the help of good language skills and communication skills.

Conclusion:

In any age, teacher plays key role in helping the society move forward. It is more relevant in 21st century. Particularly, the English teachers are playing pivotal roles across the institutions and organizations as Language trainers, Grammar trainers, Business Communication trainers, Soft Skills trainers, etc. Hence, the English language teachers must equip themselves with the latest technological devices, teaching methods, teaching – learning activities, etc.

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